

PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR THE FORMATION OF ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS IN STUDENTS BASED ON LEARNING OUTCOMES

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Abstract. *The formation of entrepreneurial skills in students based on learning outcomes is one of the important areas, which serves to train personnel suitable for the country's economy, ensure the employment of young people in the form of entrepreneurship, and develop qualified specialists in society. The political and legal framework for directing students to entrepreneurship is often determined by laws and regulatory documents. These documents cover the requirements for entrepreneurial education, the rights of young people to acquire skills, and support provided to students by the state. In our country, international programs on determining the literacy and competence of students and monitoring the quality of education provide for improving the quality of teaching in specific subjects, improving their theoretical, methodological and methodological foundations, and assessing the level of independent knowledge acquisition as a separate parameter. The reforms being implemented in the context of active innovation processes in the social and economic spheres of our society have put on the agenda one of the main trends in the development of the education system - the problem of developing entrepreneurial intellectual qualities in students in vocational and technical schools.*

Keywords: *talent, intellectual, entrepreneurship, competitiveness, education, labor market, profession, startup.*

Introduction. Guiding students towards entrepreneurship is essential in today's rapidly changing labor market, taking into account the interests and abilities of children and guiding them to choose the right entrepreneurial skills. This process plays an important role not only in determining the future of students, but also in the development of our economy. It is important that students are provided with the necessary information and skills when choosing an entrepreneurial direction, as well as studying their personal interests and talents. Such an approach serves to educate a generation of future successful professionals.

Current problems in the field. In vocational, college and technical schools, targeted training programs for gifted students in the formation of entrepreneurial skills include the following factors that they must possess:

- high-level mastery of subjects;
- computer literacy and deep knowledge of programming;
- foreign language literacy;
- acquire the skills and qualifications to think independently and express new ideas in the process of carrying out scientific and creative work;
- quickly master new developments in the field;
- acquire accurate calculations and the ability to foresee the future and acquire knowledge about new approaches;

– demonstrate oneself as a patriotic, well-rounded person who correctly understands and supports the internal and foreign policy of the state.

It is known that creating the necessary conditions for the upbringing and education of gifted students contributes to the formation of a national elite in different countries, ensures the achievements of science, art and the competitiveness of the national economy. The emergence of this talent is necessary not only for the individual, but also for society and its development. The importance of this most important strategic national task encourages a deeper study of the theoretical (concepts, types, forms of manifestation, etc.) and practical aspects (organizational forms of working with gifted children) of children's talents. Talent is the possibility of the psyche, which systematically develops throughout the life of the human psyche, and ensures that a person achieves unconventional and extraordinary results in relation to others. Talent directs all human capabilities and thinking to solve new life challenges and adapt to new conditions. The problems of searching for, revealing, educating, and educating talents are still relevant for scientists and practitioners around the world.

The accumulated enough material on the study of gifted children of different ages encourages us to think about the relationship between one or another age characteristic and the sparks of talent, as well as the course of age changes. According to the American psychologist L. Terman, “proper upbringing of gifted children” will turn them into “ideal adults” and they will succeed in real life. Therefore, preserving children’s talents is a pedagogical problem, and in fact, an educational problem. Many researchers have come to the conclusion that most gifted children have special features that distinguish them from many of their peers. The ways of knowing the world in gifted children do not always correspond to the traditional educational environment. Because for gifted children, understanding this world is a normal phenomenon that organically fits into their perception. Today, a number of problems arise in guiding students towards entrepreneurship. As a result, there is a shortage of specialists in sectors entering the labor market, and it is necessary to attract specialists from abroad.

If we do not find a comprehensive solution to this problem, this problem will take root and in the future, very large gaps may appear. First, there are misunderstandings due to parental interference in the educational organization's orientation to the formation of active entrepreneurial skills for its students who will enter the labor market in the future. Young people face social and family pressure in the formation of entrepreneurial skills and in choosing a specific direction. It is the demands of the family and those around them that force young people to choose entrepreneurship contrary to their own desires. This leads to stress for young people and the choice of entrepreneurship that does not match their abilities. Secondly, in educational institutions and families, students are not provided with information about the new entrepreneurial skills of the 21st-22nd centuries. Unfortunately, parents

advocates for their children to become owners of popular areas such as medicine, banking, economics, prosecutor's office, internal affairs, law, and teaching. However, parents are not aware of the increasing demand for these and other areas in the next 10 years, including GMO agronomists, blockchain systems specialists, cybersecurity administrators, cyberprostheses and implants developers, marketers, bioengineers, telemedicine, 3D designers, VR programmers, artificial intelligence engineers, drone operators, and modern entrepreneurship. Thirdly, it is also common in practice that psychologists in educational institutions and consultants in specialized educational institutions do not properly organize promotional work with students about future

entrepreneurial skills. Fourthly, there are artificial barriers to women and men working in these areas based on gender stereotypes.

Experience shows that in the Uzbek mentality, some areas of entrepreneurship are designated for women, and others for men. This is reflected in the fact that in families, fathers or mothers force daughters to choose a narrow range of areas when forming and choosing entrepreneurial skills. In education, it has also been observed that more boys choose the exact sciences and more girls choose the natural sciences. As clear evidence of this, when analyzing students studying in the exact and natural sciences in the system of the Agency for Specialized Educational Institutions in the 2024-2025 academic year, it was revealed that there are imbalances. In particular, in the natural sciences, 38% are boys and 62% are girls, while in the exact sciences, 37% are girls and 63% are boys.

1. Advanced foreign experience in this area

Problems in the formation and orientation of students' entrepreneurial skills and advanced foreign experiences in solving them. The formation and orientation of students' entrepreneurial skills plays an important role in the integration of the education system and the labor market. In world experience, there are various models and approaches to effectively implement this process. Taking into account the existing problems in Uzbekistan, it is advisable to study and implement the following advanced foreign experiences.

1. German experience: In Germany, a “dual education system” has been introduced, which ensures that students simultaneously receive education and participate in the production process. 70% of the training is aimed at internships in enterprises and organizations. Enterprises participating in the training process are obliged to provide employment to young specialists, and employers are directly involved in the development of training programs to develop entrepreneurial skills.

2. Finnish experience. In Finland, “career counselors” operate in every school and guide students according to their personal interests, students are advised on the formation of entrepreneurial skills from the moment they enter education, educational organizations and centers work together, preparing students for real labor market conditions. This experience is now being introduced in colleges, lyceums, technical schools in the system, and practical work is being carried out in this area.

3. Japanese experience, Japanese educational institutions pay great attention to STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics), entrepreneurship education is focused on areas such as robotics, artificial intelligence, and programming. Advanced technologies and interactive methods are used in the learning process.

4. USA experience - increasing private sector participation in entrepreneurship education In the USA, the participation of the private sector in the development of education in the formation of entrepreneurial skills is important, large manufacturing companies provide grants to technical schools and vocational colleges. Agreements are concluded between enterprises and educational institutions, and graduates are provided with guaranteed jobs.

2. Proposals for solving these problems

The following proposals can be put forward to solve the above problems. The following are proposed as solutions: It is advisable to introduce an educational organization consultant responsible for guiding students in the formation of entrepreneurial skills in almost every district or city, where there are colleges, vocational schools, and technical schools. It would be advisable for the consultants of this educational organization to carry out promotional work in each

educational organization or neighborhood, in collaboration with activists, on the formation of new entrepreneurial skills that will enter the labor market in the future. The demand for labor resources in the global market is changing dramatically. Currently, the need for specialists in such areas as robotics, artificial intelligence, biotechnology, digital marketing, and creative industries is increasing. Therefore, targeted training of young people in these areas is of great importance. Fundamental measures must be taken to ensure that the Uzbek education system adapts to these changes.

Proposals:

Firstly, redeveloping vocational education standards, including the skills necessary for 21st-22nd century professions and entrepreneurship (soft skills, critical thinking, data analytics, creativity, entrepreneurship, IT) in the curriculum, introducing the subject “21st-22nd century skills” in schools. Widely using the Project-Based Learning method in educational processes. Secondly, organizing practical training on digital literacy, cybersecurity and artificial intelligence. Thirdly, strengthening cooperation between employers and educational institutions. Developing specialized programs in collaboration with enterprises. Integrating the business and startup ecosystem with education. Fourthly, it would be appropriate to create opportunities for dual education and cooperation with production so that college, technical school, vocational school and university students spend 50% of their time in practical training in production. Fifth, expand Internship and Apprenticeship programs. Make it mandatory for every student to complete at least one internship.

Organize events such as the “Start-up Challenge” for young people in collaboration with startups and business incubators. Sixth, increase attention to STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics) education by introducing IT, artificial intelligence, robotics, cybersecurity, and data analysis courses in schools. Organize programs such as “Coding for Kids” and “AI for Beginners.” Organize research laboratories at universities. Expand grant programs for young engineers and researchers. Seventh, develop “EdTech” (Educational Technology) platforms. Online education for students developing courses. Creating personalized learning platforms using artificial intelligence to develop distance learning.

Conclusion.

The formation and orientation of students in entrepreneurial skills is one of the important directions of the education system, which serves to train personnel suitable for the country's economy, ensure youth employment, and produce qualified specialists in society. The demand for labor resources in the global market is changing dramatically. Currently, the need for specialists in such areas as robotics, artificial intelligence, biotechnology, digital marketing, and creative industries is increasing.

Therefore, targeted training of young people in these areas is of great importance. Fundamental measures must be taken to ensure that the education system of Uzbekistan adapts to these changes. The formation of entrepreneurial skills is one of the most important decisions that affects the future of each person. The role of parents in this process is of great importance, because they are the first mentors and guides for their children.

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